

Soil and crop management

Effect of herbicides on azolla

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A randomized complete block design with three replications was used to determine the effect of some herbicides on azolla (*Azolla pinnata* R. Br.) in transplanted rice. Azolla at a rate of 300 g fresh weight/m² was inoculated into plots immediately after transplanting. The rates and times of herbicide application are shown in the table.

All herbicides used were deleterious to azolla and caused a significant reduction in fresh weight 30 days after transplanting (DT) (see table). Of those applied 4 DT, 2,4-D caused the least reduction in growth. Propanil was more detrimental than 2,4-D applied 21 DT.

When 2,4-D was applied 4 DT, there

Fresh weight (g/m²) of azolla 30 days after transplanting as affected by herbicide application. IRRI, 1980 wet season.

Treatment	Rate of application (kg/ha)	Time of application (DT) ^a	Azolla fresh wt ^b (g/m ²)	
Thiobencarb	1.0	4	418.0	d
Propanil	3.0	21	536.3	d
Piperophos - 2,4-D	1.5	4	667.7	cd
Butachlor	1.0	4	814.3	cd
2,4-D (liquid)	0.5	21	1420.6	bc
2,4-D (granule)	0.8	4	1660.3	b
Untreated	—	—	2840.0	a

^aDT = days after transplanting. ^bMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

was a general thickening of the azolla layer, followed by yellowing of the plants and localized death. Eventually, some recovery was observed. With other herbicides applied 4 DT, the azolla layer turned red or purple, then black. Virtually no recovery occurred.

Of the herbicides applied 21 DT, propanil was more rapid in action than 2,4-D. No recovery was observed in

either plot 9 days later.

From these results, it appears unlikely that herbicides can be used for weed control when rice is to be inoculated with azolla. The weeds will have to be controlled by other means, such as by the suppressive effect of azolla itself, by hand weeding or by using a rotary weeder at the time azolla is incorporated into the soil. ■

Azolla influence on rice yield

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The effect of azolla on paddy rice yields was studied in June-September and October-February 1980-81. A randomized block design with 10 treatments and 3 replications examined the effect of different levels of nitrogen (N) and nitrogen plus azolla. Phosphorus (P₂O₅) and potassium (K₂O) were applied uniformly at 50-50 kg/ha as basal dressing. Spacing was 20 × 10 cm.

Azolla was applied at 300 g/m² on the week after transplanting and incorporated 15 days later. Variety TKM9 was raised in the first season and IR20 in the second.

Azolla contributed to yield increase in both seasons (Table 1). In the first season, the yield with 50 kg N/ha + azolla equaled that with 75 kg N/ha. A similar trend with 25 kg N + azolla and 50 kg N/ha was seen in the second season.

Table 1. Effect of azolla on yield at Ambasamudram, India, 1980-81.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Jun-Sep		Oct-Feb	
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Increase over control (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Increase over control (%)
0 N (control)	8.6	—	4.5	—
0 N + azolla	8.8	2.3	4.7	4.4
25 N	9.0	4.7	4.9	8.9
25 N + azolla	9.0	4.7	5.0	11.1
50 N	9.2	7.0	4.9	8.9
50 N + azolla	9.4	9.3	5.0	11.1
75 N	9.4	9.3	5.2	15.6
75 N + azolla	9.7	12.8	5.4	20.0
100 N	9.0	4.7	5.3	17.8
100 N + azolla	9.7	12.8	5.5	22.2
CD (<i>P</i> = 0.05)	ns		0.49	

Table 2. Azolla weight and multiplication ratio at Ambasamudram, India, 1980-81.

Treatment	Azolla mean weight (kg)	Multiplication ratio for 16 days
200 g azolla + 50 g superphosphate	1.8	9.0
200 g azolla + 100 g superphosphate	1.8	9.3
400 g azolla + 50 g superphosphate	2.0	4.9
400 g azolla + 100 g superphosphate	2.1	5.2
800 g azolla + 50 g superphosphate	2.2	2.7
800 g azolla + 100 g superphosphate	2.2	2.8
1,600 g azolla + 50 g superphosphate	2.4	1.5
1,600 g azolla + 100 g superphosphate	2.3	1.5